

THE MAIN DIFFICULTIES OF LEARNING LISTENING AND WAYS TO OVERCOME THEM

Avazov Sanjar Berdiyevich

Teacher of foreign languages at Academic Lyceum of Termiz State University
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7619315>

Annotation: The article considered that listening is a complex analytical and synthetic activity, the success of which depends on the listener himself, on the development of his speech hearing and memory, on his attention, interest, etc., as well as on the conditions of perception of temporal characteristics, the number of presentations, and, finally, on language features, their correspondence to speech experience and the knowledge of the students.

Keywords: Learning listening, the basis of communication, speech activity, ways of thinking, teaching children, related to memory activity, pronunciation training.

In recent years, the importance of the English language has increased in our country. Modern enterprises in our country are in need of highly qualified specialists who can not only read and write, but also communicate in a foreign language. A foreign language is an important element of universal culture and a necessary condition for integration into the world educational system. Therefore, knowledge of a foreign language is useful both for society as a whole and for an individual. Its study contributes to the inclusion of the individual in the socio-political and cultural life of the country [1:5].

English is one of the most popular and sought-after languages around the world. The number of native English speakers is more than 400 million people who speak it (including those who use it as a second language) about 1 billion people. English is the language of international trade, tourism, politics and the Internet. This is the first and main language of world communication. Speaking English, you can discover a lot of new things. There is no need to hire translators when traveling abroad, to look for translations of original articles and books. English will expand your knowledge and understanding of the world. That is why so much space is allocated for its study in educational institutions [4:12].

One of the main tasks of a teacher is to teach children listening skills. After all, in order to learn English, we have to listen a lot and accurately perceive the information received. Often, in addition to hearing speech, it is necessary to perform other actions: observe, speak, write, etc., but for the most part, in order to function adequately in a particular situation, it is necessary to understand what you have heard [5:124].

The problem of teaching listening is one of the most relevant topics in the modern methodology of teaching English, since without the development of auditory skills it is impossible to develop other types of speech activity. Such as reading, speaking and writing. Underestimating listening skills can have an extremely negative impact on the language training of schoolchildren [5:125]. It is also known that listening is a very difficult type of speech activity. Lack of formation of auditory skills is often the cause of communication disorders.

Hence, the importance and relevance of the problem of teaching listening is obvious.

Understand the main content of short, uncomplicated authentic texts (weather forecast, TV/radio programs, announcements at the train station/airport) and highlight meaningful information;

- understand the main content of simple authentic texts related to different communicative types of speech (message/story);
- be able to determine the subject of the text, highlight the main facts, omitting the secondary ones;
- use a repeat question, a request to repeat.

In this part, we will consider the features of listening as a type of speech activity. According to the definition of Rogova G.V. and Vereshchagina I.N., "listening" is the understanding of speech perceived by ear. It is a perceptual mental mnemonic activity. Perceptual – because perception, reception, perception is carried out; mental – because its implementation is associated with basic mental operations: analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, comparison, abstraction, concretization, etc.; mnemonic – because there is a selection and assimilation of informative features, image formation, recognition, recognition as a result of comparison with the standard stored in memory. Galskova N.D. and Gez N.I. characterized "listening" as a complex receptive thought-related activity associated with the perception, understanding and active processing of information contained in an oral speech message [6:161].

Listening is the basis of communication, and the mastery of oral communication begins with it. It consists of the ability to differentiate perceived sounds, integrate them into semantic complexes, keep them in memory during listening, carry out probabilistic forecasting and, based on the communication situation, understand the perceived sound chain. At the same time, the process of perception takes place at a certain normal pace, characteristic of a given language, from different sources, with natural interference of a speech and non-speech nature.

Listening is also a powerful means of teaching a foreign language. It makes it possible to master the sound side of the language being studied, its phonemic composition and intonation: rhythm, stress and melody. Through listening is the assimilation of the lexical composition of the language and its grammatical structure. At the same time, listening facilitates the mastery of speaking, reading and writing, which is one of the main reasons for using listening as an auxiliary, and sometimes the main means of teaching these types of speech activity [2:42].

Understanding speech by ear is closely related to speaking – the expression of thoughts by means of the language being studied [6:27]. Speaking and listening are two interrelated aspects of oral speech. The phases of listening and speaking in communication are interspersed. Listening is not only the reception of a message, but also the preparation in internal speech of a response to what is heard. Thus, speaking helps to form the perception of speech by ear.

Listening is also connected with reading. They are united by belonging to receptive types of speech activity, when perception – understanding – active processing of information obtained from speech messages occurs – when listening through the auditory channel, when reading – through the visual channel. Reading is the translation of a graphic language into a sound one. Reading – aloud or to himself, a person hears the perceived text.

Listening is also most closely related to writing. In the process of graphic design, a person pronounces and hears what he writes [3:21].

Thus, being closely related to other types of speech activity, listening plays an important role in learning a foreign language and especially in communication-oriented learning. The modern methodology of teaching foreign languages both in our country and in other countries emphasizes the need for the formation of listening as a very important skill, without mastering which communication in the language is unthinkable. Listening should take an important place already at the initial stage. And underestimating listening skills can have an extremely negative impact on the language training of schoolchildren.

Of particular importance in listening are different ways of thinking and representing the world in the form of visual, sound and tactile images. This problem is the object of research in modern psychology, which is called "neuro-linguistic programming". It explores how a person sees, hears, feels.

Perceiving speech, the listener transforms sound images into articulatory ones with the help of a motor (speech-motor) analyzer. A strong functional connection is established between the auditory analyzer and the speech motor apparatus. As for the visual analyzer, it is known that optical signals are superior

to all others in obtaining information about the outside world. When listening, the visual analyzer greatly facilitates the perception and understanding of speech by ear. Such visual supports as speech organs, gestures, facial expressions, kinemas and others reinforce auditory sensations, facilitate internal pronunciation and understanding of the meaning of speech.

Intonation is considered to be the most informative feature, since it has "perceived qualities", thanks to which the auditor can segment speech into syntactic blocks, understand the connection of parts of a phrase, and, consequently, reveal the content, hence the idea of intonation as one of the landmarks in understanding speech by ear, such speech functions as communicative, syntactic, logical, modal. When perceiving speech messages, first of all, the communicative plan of the utterance is recognized, and intonation is one of the main structural features by which the communicative types of sentences are distinguished: narration, question, exclamation and prompting.

At the phonetic level, the success of anticipation is determined by knowledge of the probabilistic sound sequence and is reduced to choosing the optimal solution about the sound. If the initial and final parts of a word are the most informative in visual perception, then when listening, the initial sounds and those located in the middle, if they are stressed, become the most important for understanding. Sounds carry more informative load in short words than in long ones. This obviously explains the special complexity of their recognition.

The understanding of words depends on the knowledge of the semanticosyntactic valence of words and the laws of their word formation, on the ability to correlate the meanings of words, especially polysemous ones, with the context.

The psychological basis of understanding is the processes of perception, recognition of language images, understanding of their meanings, the processes of anticipation (guessing) and comprehension of information, the processes of grouping information, their generalization, retention of information in memory, the processes of inference.

The nature of forecasting and understanding is determined by the level of language proficiency and, accordingly, the level of development of speech hearing at this stage, audit experience and awareness of the topic. All these components of listening allow a person to actualize auditory patterns of a linguistic phenomenon (words and intonation models), its generalized paradigmatic and syntactic structures, thereby ensuring correct prediction and subsequent sense formation.

Forecasting at the text level is associated with additional difficulties. Even an experienced auditor is not always able to retain all the information, combine disparate facts into a common context, understand the motives and hidden meaning of the message. This requires a focus of attention, interest in the subject of the message, a certain speed of mental processing of information.

In a word, listening, connected with the understanding of other people's thoughts and the idea underlying the utterance, presupposes a sufficiently high level of development of lexical, grammatical and phonetic automatisms. Only under this condition can the listener's attention be focused on the content.

Listening to speech messages is associated with memory activity. Memory, along with sensations, perception and imagination, is attributed to a person's sensitive cognition of the surrounding world. In contrast, thinking and speech are called methods of rational cognition of the world.

Let's consider imagination and memory as cognitive processes. Imagination can be defined as the ability of a person to willfully restore and present in a figurative form those sensations and perceptions that were before, or to invent and present something new that was not there before either in sensations or in perception. The images of the imagination do not necessarily have to correspond to what they really are. In contrast, memory images usually correspond to one degree or another to the reality they reflect, and almost do not carry elements of fantasy.

The very concept of "memory" can be dissected. *Short-term memory* is a method of storing information for a short period of time; *efficient* is called memory designed to store information for a certain, predetermined period, ranging from a few seconds to several days; *long-term is memory* capable of storing information for an almost unlimited period. When using it to recall, thinking and willpower are often required. A small child in elementary school has a well-developed long-term memory. Therefore, an early age is most preferable in learning a foreign language. Everything that the child has learned is remembered for a long time. Visual memory is associated with the preservation and reproduction of visual images. This type of memory assumes a person's developed ability to imagine; auditory memory is a good memorization and accurate reproduction of various sounds, musical and speech, characterized by the fact that a person can quickly and accurately remember the meaning of the text presented to him, etc. Emotional memory is a memory for experiences. The strength of memorization of the material is directly based on it. What causes

emotional experiences in a person is remembered by them without much difficulty and for a longer period.

These types of memory play a fundamental role in learning listening, without their sufficient development it is impossible to master language in general, and even more so speech.

The process of listening to speech is characterized by an active purposeful nature associated with the performance of complex mental and psychological activities, the success of which is facilitated by a high degree of concentration of attention. Attention arises with the help of emotions and develops at their expense, but in a person emotions always manifest themselves in unity with the volitional process.

As you know, speech is the main component of thinking. Correct reading is impossible without mastering listening, since during reading, both aloud and "to himself", a person uses speech, and in the latter case – internal speech, it allows him to control himself and the correctness of his statements. Based on this, we can conclude that without mastering speech in all its forms, it is impossible to learn to read correctly, and listening is a great way to train pronunciation. The situation is similar with writing, where, along with a person's memory, inner speech also works, and, without realizing it, a person pronounces what he writes. As for speaking, as already mentioned above, it is not possible without the ability to listen and understand the interlocutor's speech, and since the main forms of communication in a foreign language lesson are dialogue and monologue, listening instruction is very important for students' free communication.

Thus, we see that listening as a type of speech activity plays an important role at the initial stage and serves as an effective means of teaching English at school.

References:

1. Babinskaya P.K. Practical course of methods of teaching foreign languages: textbook / P.K. Babinskaya, T.M. Leontieva, A.F. Budko. – 3rd ed. – M.: Tetra System, 2005.
2. Galskova N.D., Gez N.I. Theory of teaching a foreign language. Linguodidactics and methodology.
3. Kolker Ya.M. Practical methods of teaching a foreign language. – M., 2000
4. Karavanova N.B. English from scratch/ N.B.Karavanova. – M.: Eskimo, 2013. – 320s.
5. Solovova E. N. Methods of teaching foreign languages: A basic course of lectures: A manual for students of pedagogical colleges and teachers / E. N. Solovova. M.: Enlightenment, 2002.

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

6. Shafoatovich, R. K. (2021). Unique ways to organize the first piano lessons for adults. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(11), 259-261.
7. Rakhmatullaev, H. S. (2022). Music, Man and Artificial Intelligence. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY*, 3(12), 93-96.
8. Shafoatovich, R. H. (2022). The Study of the Historical Roots of the Art of Bakhshi by Means of Words and Music. *International Journal of Culture and Modernity*, 15, 45-47.
9. Raxmatullaev, X. S. (2022). Tarixgacha bo'lgan davrlarda musiqa. *Science and Education*, 3(11), 821-825.
10. Raxmatullayev, X. S. (2022). BORBAD MARVAZIY FORS VA TURKIY XALQLAR MUSIQASI ISLOHOTCHISI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(10), 1262-1270.
11. Theoretical foundations of methods of teaching a foreign language in secondary school. / [Text]: Ed. Klimentenko A.D., Mirolyubova A.A. M., Pedagogy.1981.